

A Comparative Study of TGT and PGT Teachers' Attitudes Toward Inclusive Education in Schools: A Multi-Dimensional Analysis

Sana¹, Saroj Malik², Khushnuda Bano³

¹Student, Delhi Teachers University, Delhi, 2334sana.khan@gmail.com

²Associate Professor, Delhi Teachers University, Delhi, sarojmalik8@gmail.com

³Academic Consultant, CIET-NCERT, Delhi, khushnuda5180@gmail.com

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20687950>

ARTICLE DETAILS

Research Paper

Accepted: 24-05-2026

Published: 10-06-2026

Keywords:

*Inclusive Education,
Teacher Education,
Teachers' Attitudes,
TASTIE-SA, Trained
Graduate Teachers (TGTs),
Post Graduate Teachers
(PGTs)*

ABSTRACT

Despite significant advancement in inclusive education, understanding the attitudinal differences between teachers with varying qualifications remains a critical area requiring investigation. This study examined the attitudes of secondary school teachers toward inclusive education across four key dimensions: psychological and behavioral, social and parental, curricular and co-curricular, and administrative aspects. It aimed to compare attitudes between Trained Graduate Teachers (TGTs) and Post Graduate Teachers (PGTs) and also to explore the influence of demographic variables. A descriptive survey research design was employed with a sample comprised 84 secondary-level school teachers, including 48 TGTs and 36 PGTs, selected through the snowball-cum-purposive sampling technique. Data were collected using the standardized TASTIE-SA (Teacher Attitude Scale Toward Inclusive Education) developed by Dr. Vishal Sood and Dr. Arti Anand, administered via Google Forms. The tool used a three-point Likert scale (Agree, Undecided, Disagree). Five hypotheses were tested to examine significant differences between TGT and PGT teachers across overall attitudes and specific dimensional components. The findings revealed non-significant differences between groups and dimensional analysis. This study has provided valuable insights into the attitudes of secondary

school teachers toward inclusive education, revealing significant similarities between TGT and PGT teachers across all measured dimensions. The findings challenge common assumptions about the relationship between educational qualifications and professional attitudes, suggesting that other factors may be more influential in shaping teacher perspectives on inclusive education. Future research should examine longitudinal changes to enhance understanding of inclusive education implementation in diverse school contexts.

Introduction

Inclusive education has emerged as a fundamental principle in global educational discourse, focusing to ensure equitable and qualitative learning opportunities for each and every learner, irrespective of their calibre, capabilities, backgrounds, or needs. Grounded in the principles of social justice and equitable participation, inclusive education promotes the inclusion of all learners within mainstream classroom environments.

In the Indian context, this paradigm has gained significant policies support through legislative frameworks such as the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (RPWD) Act, 2016, and the National Education Policy (NEP), 2020. Both emphasize not only access to education but also meaningful participation through systemic transformation in curriculum, pedagogy, and institutional practices.

Teachers play a key role in the effective implementation of strategies for inclusive education. Their attitudes, beliefs, and instructional practices significantly influence the extent to which inclusive strategies are successfully adopted in classroom settings. Empirical evidence manifests that teacher attitudes toward inclusion are shaped by multiple factors, including professional designation, teaching experience, gender, institutional role, support, and access to professional training.

Yadav (2023) and Makwana (2022) emphasize the importance of educating children with special needs alongside their peers in regular classrooms to ensure equality and social integration. Bhattacharjee (2021) identifies significant barriers such as inadequate infrastructure, limited assistive technologies, and a shortage of trained educators, while also highlighting the role of stakeholders' attitudes in shaping inclusive practices. Similarly, Hossain (2021) underscores both the opportunities and challenges associated with inclusive education in India, highlighting the importance of legislative support such as the Right to Education Act (2009). Mishra and Negari (2021) highlighted the persistent gap between

policy recommendations and practical implementation, emphasizing the need for stronger institutional mechanisms and affirmative action to ensure equitable educational opportunities. Mehta (2020) advocates for learner-centered pedagogies, creativity, and adaptive teaching approaches to address diverse learning needs within inclusive classrooms.

International perspectives further reinforce these findings; Madhesh (2023) and Kurowski et al. (2022) identify structural and pedagogical barriers, including social dynamics and institutional constraints, that hinder effective inclusion. The role of collaboration and support systems has also been emphasized in the literature. Mann and Gilmore (2021) highlight the importance of effective parent–teacher partnerships in enhancing student outcomes, particularly for learners with disabilities. Similarly, Parey (2021) identifies both positive and negative teacher attitudes toward inclusion, linking them to humanistic beliefs, perceived benefits, and concerns regarding institutional support. Safdar and Rashid (2021) further emphasize the importance of pre-service and in-service teacher training in preparing educators for inclusive classrooms.

Despite the expanding body of research, there remains a paucity of empirical studies in the Indian context that systematically examine teacher attitudes using standardized measurement tools across multiple dimensions. Moreover, limited attention has been given to the comparative analysis of teacher attitudes based on professional designation and demographic variables.

In response to these gaps, the present study seeks to assess the attitudes of secondary school teachers toward inclusive education using the standardized Teacher Attitude Scale Toward Inclusive Education (TASTIE-SA). The study examines attitudes across four dimensions; psychological and behavioural, social and parental, curricular and co-curricular, and administrative aspects and analyzes differences based on designation (TGT vs. PGT) and selected demographic variables.

By providing a multidimensional and comparative analysis, the study aims to contribute to the existing literature and offer insights that can inform teacher education programs, institutional practices, and policy frameworks for the effective implementation of inclusive education.

Need and Rationale of the Study

Although the literature on inclusive education is steadily growing, there is a lack of empirical research in the Indian context that offers a multi-dimensional analysis of teacher attitudes using validated and structured tools such as the Teacher Attitude Scale Toward Inclusive Education (TASTIE-SA). Most existing studies either employ generalized surveys or rely on researcher-developed questionnaires, which

often lack psychometric validation and may not capture the nuanced realities of diverse teaching populations.

Also there is a scarcity of studies that explore differences in teacher attitudes based on variables such as designation (TGT vs. PGT), gender, school type, and years of teaching experience, especially using a consistent theoretical and methodological framework. This gap limits the potential of research to inform targeted interventions in teacher education and policy.

This study contributes localized evidence by gathering responses from secondary school teachers in a specific regional context. It provides context-sensitive insights that can guide school leaders, educational authorities, and curriculum planners in enhancing inclusive practices at the grassroots level. The study also fills an important gap in comparative analysis by systematically investigating attitudinal differences between TGTs and PGTs, as well as across different types of schools, within a unified empirical framework.

Objectives of the Study To examine the overall attitudes of secondary school teachers toward inclusive education across its key dimensions:

- a. psychological and behavioural,
 - b. social and parental,
 - c. curricular and co-curricular,
 - d. administrative aspects.
2. To analyze the differences in attitudes toward inclusive education between TGTs (Trained Graduate Teachers) and PGTs (Post Graduate Teachers).
 3. To explore whether demographic characteristics, such as gender, educational background, teaching experience, and school type can influence teachers' attitudes toward inclusive education.

Hypotheses of the Study

In the present study, the researcher formulated five hypotheses (H1 to H5) and five null hypotheses (H_01 to H_05) to examine differences in teachers' attitudes toward inclusive education based on selected demographic variables. These hypotheses were tested using inferential statistical techniques, specifically

the independent samples t-test, as the study involved comparing the means of two independent groups for each variable.

The significance of differences in mean attitude scores was assessed at the 0.05 level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$). A 5% significance level reflects the accepted probability of mistakenly identifying a difference when none actually exists, which is a common benchmark in educational research. A p-value equal to or less than 0.05 was considered the threshold for determining statistical significance.

The hypotheses tested were as follows:

H1: TGTs and PGTs will differ significantly in overall attitudes toward inclusive education.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the overall attitudes of TGTs and PGTs toward inclusive education.

H2: TGTs and PGTs will differ significantly in their attitudes regarding the psychological and behavioral components of inclusive education.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between TGTs and PGTs in their attitudes toward the psychological and behavioral aspects of inclusive education.

H3: TGTs and PGTs will differ significantly in their attitudes toward the social and parental involvement in inclusive education.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference between TGTs and PGTs in their attitudes toward the social and parental dimensions of inclusive education.

H4: TGTs and PGTs will differ significantly in their attitudes toward the curricular and co-curricular aspects of inclusive education.

H₀₄: There is no significant difference between TGTs and PGTs in the attitudes concerning the curricular and co-curricular aspects of inclusive education.

H5: TGTs and PGTs will differ significantly in their attitudes toward the administrative aspects of inclusive education.

H₀₅: There is no significant difference between TGTs and PGTs in their attitudes concerning the administrative aspects related to inclusive education.

For each hypothesis, the independent samples t-test was applied to compare the group-wise means of the total attitude scores and sub-dimension scores of the TASTIE scale. Based on the calculated t-values and associated p-values, the hypotheses were either accepted (if $p \leq 0.05$) or not accepted (if $p > 0.05$). This approach ensured an objective and statistically sound basis for interpreting the differences between teacher groups with respect to their attitudes toward inclusive education.

Methodology

This study, employed a descriptive survey research design that is best to explore and analyze the attitude of teachers toward inclusive education across different school contexts (Behavioral/Psychological aspect, Social and Parental aspect, Curricular and Co-curricular aspect and Administrative Aspect).

Population of the Study

The population of the present study comprised Trained Graduate Teachers (TGTs) and Post Graduate Teachers (PGTs) working in schools. These groups were chosen as they represent two key categories of secondary school teachers who play a crucial role in implementing inclusive education practices at different levels of schooling.

Sample Size

In this study, a total of 84 secondary-level school teachers participated, including 48 Trained Graduate Teachers (TGTs) and 36 Post Graduate Teachers (PGTs). The sample was drawn using a snowball-cum-purposive sampling technique, which allowed the researcher to reach educators actively involved in teaching at the middle and senior secondary levels; those most likely to have practical experience with inclusive education policies and practices.

Sampling Technique

To recruit participants for the present study, the researcher utilized a combination of purposive and snowball sampling techniques. This blended approach was chosen to allow for both intentional participant selection and an expanded reach within a specific target group teachers at the secondary and senior secondary levels who are actively involved in classroom teaching and are likely to have relevant experiences related to inclusive education.

Data Collection Tool

The data collection tool utilized to assess teachers' attitudes toward inclusive education in schools was the TASTIE-SA (Teacher Attitude Scale Toward Inclusive Education), a standardized scale developed by Dr. Vishal Sood and Dr. (Mrs.) Arti Anand. The TASTIE-SA attitude scale was developed using the summated ratings method proposed by Likert (1932). Each item on the scale is rated on a three-point scale: Agree, Undecided, and Disagree. The overall attitude score of a teacher is derived by summing the individual ratings assigned to each statement on the scale.

Procedure

The process began by sharing a Google Form version of the TASTIE-SA scale with a group of educators through formal WhatsApp messages. These initial participants were purposefully selected based on their teaching designations (TGTs and PGTs) and their current engagement in teaching roles. This reflects the purposive sampling component, wherein individuals were chosen because they met specific, predefined criteria that aligned with the study's focus.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

The collected data were analyzed using quantitative statistical techniques, as the tool used (TASTIE-SA) yields numerical scores that reflect various sub-dimensions of teachers' attitudes toward inclusive education. The data were first downloaded from Google Forms in Excel format. The analysis involved several key steps: Data Cleaning and Coding and Descriptive Statistics.

Delimitations of the Study

1. The study was confined to TGTs and PGTs only; other categories such as PRT/SGT were excluded.
2. The data were collected through snowball-cum-purposive sampling, which may not fully represent the entire population of teachers.
3. The sample size was limited to 84 teachers (48 TGTs and 36 PGTs), based on accessibility and willingness to participate.
4. The study was restricted to teachers who responded via Google Forms circulated on WhatsApp, thereby excluding those without access to or familiarity with this mode of data collection.

5. The study focused only on teachers’ attitudes toward inclusive education, measured using the *Teacher Attitude Scale Toward Inclusive Education* by Dr. Vishal Sood and Dr. Arti Anand, and did not examine other related aspects such as classroom practices or student outcomes.

Results and Discussion

The findings of the present study are present and discussed below:

The first section presents the demographic profile of the teachers and the second section focuses on the hypotheses testing of attitudes of teachers toward inclusive education, as measured by the Teacher Attitude Scale Toward Inclusive Education (TASTIE-SA).

Demographics

Table 1 displayed the distribution of respondents based on their highest educational qualifications categorized into TGT graduate, TGT postgraduate and PGT postgraduate levels.

Table 1: Educational Qualification-wise Distribution

Educational Qualification-wise Distribution of Respondents		
Educational Qualification	Frequency	Percentage
TGT Graduate	14	16.67%
TGT Postgraduate	34	40.48%
PGT Postgraduate	36	42.86%

Figure 1a — Frequency distribution

Figure 1b — Percentage share

Figure 1. Educational qualification-wise distribution of respondents (N = 84).

Out of the total 84 respondents, 14 (16.67%) were TGTs with graduate qualifications, and 34 (40.48%) were TGTs with postgraduate qualifications. 36 respondents (42.86%) were PGTs, all of whom held postgraduate degrees. This distribution indicates that the majority of respondents were postgraduates, with PGTs forming the largest group, followed by TGT postgraduates, while a smaller proportion of TGTs held only graduate-level qualifications.

Table 2 represented the Area-wise distribution, categorized by urban and rural school locations.

Table 2: Area-wise Distribution

Area-wise Distribution of Respondents		
Area	Frequency	Percentage
Urban	70	83.33%
Rural	14	16.67%

Figure 2a — Frequency distribution

Figure 2b — Percentage share

Figure 2. Area-wise distribution of respondents (N = 84).

The data reveals that out of the total 84 respondents, 70 (83.33%) were from urban areas, while only 14 (16.67%) belonged to rural areas. This indicates that the sample predominantly comprised teachers working in urban settings, highlighting a significant urban representation in the study.

Table 3 represents the gender-wise distribution of all respondents.

Table 3: Gender-wise Distribution

Gender-wise distribution of TGT and PGT Respondents			
Category	Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Overall	Male	41	48.81%
	Female	43	51.19%
TGT	Male	24	28.57%

	Female	24	28.57%
PGT	Male	17	20.24%
	Female	19	22.62%
Total		84	100%

Fig. 3: Gender-wise Distribution

Among the total of 84 participants, 41 (48.81%) identified as male, while 43 (51.19%) identified as female. The data reflects a fairly balanced gender representation in the sample, with a slightly higher proportion of female respondents compared to male respondents.

Further disaggregates the gender distribution across the two teacher categories — Trained Graduate Teachers (TGTs) and Post Graduate Teachers (PGTs). Among the 84 participants, both TGT male and TGT female respondents were equally represented, with 24 respondents each (28.57%). Among PGT respondents, 17 were male (20.24%) and 19 were female (22.62%). The data indicates a balanced gender

distribution among TGT teachers and a slightly higher number of female respondents among PGT teachers.

The merged analysis of both tables reveals that female respondents outnumbered male respondents in both the overall sample and within the PGT category, while TGTs maintained absolute gender equality. This balanced representation strengthens the generalizability of the findings, as the data does not exhibit a significant gender skew that could introduce sampling bias. The near-parity across both teacher categories also ensures that any gender-based comparisons drawn from this study would rest on a reasonably equitable distributional foundation.

Table 4 represents the designation-wise distribution of the respondents.

Table 4: Designation-wise Distribution

Designation-wise Distribution of Respondents		
Designation	Frequency	Percentage
TGT Teachers	48	57.14
PGT Teachers	36	42.86

Fig. 1 — Designation-wise distribution (N = 84)

Fig. 2 — Frequency by designation (N = 84)

Fig. 4: Designation-wise Distribution

Out of the total 84 participants, 48 respondents (57.14%) were Trained Graduate Teachers (TGT), while 36 respondents (42.86%) were Post Graduate Teachers (PGT). It indicates that the sample had a higher proportion of TGT teachers compared to PGT teachers.

Table 5 represents the distribution of respondents based on their teaching experience.

Table 5: Teaching Experience

Teaching Experience of TGTs and PGTs				
Teaching Experience (in years)	TGTs Frequency	PGTs Frequency	Combined Frequency	Overall Percentage
1-5 years	16	6	22	26.19
6-10 years	13	10	23	27.38
11-15 years	8	6	14	16.67
Above 15 years	11	14	25	29.78
Total	48	36	84	100%

Fig. 5: Teaching Experience

Out of the total 84 respondents, 22 teachers (26.19%) had 1–5 years of experience, while 23 teachers (27.38%) had 6–10 years of experience. Regarding teaching experience, 14 respondents (16.67%) reported having 11 to 15 years of service, whereas 25 participants (29.79%) had more than 15 years of teaching experience. It indicates that the sample includes a diverse range of teaching experience, with the highest proportion of respondents having over 15 years of experience.

Out of 48 TGT participants, 16 (33.33%) had been teaching for 1–5 years, 13 (27.08%) for 6–10 years, and 8 (16.67%) for 11–15 years. Additionally, 11 respondents (22.92%) reported having more than 15 years of teaching experience. This distribution highlights that a significant portion of TGT teachers in the sample were relatively early in their careers, with one-third having 1–5 years of experience.

Among the 36 Post Graduate Teacher (PGT) respondents, 6 teachers (16.67%) had 1–5 years of experience, 10 (27.78%) had 6–10 years, and another 6 (16.67%) had been teaching for 11–15 years. Notably, 14 respondents (38.89%) reported having more than 15 years of teaching experience. This indicates that the majority of PGT teachers in the sample were highly experienced, with a significant portion having over 15 years in the profession.

These findings suggest that while TGTs are relatively more concentrated in the early stages of their professional careers, PGTs are predominantly seasoned educators with extensive teaching experience. This disparity in experiential background may have meaningful implications for the study's core investigation, as teaching experience is widely recognized in educational research as a significant variable influencing teachers' attitudes, perceptions, and readiness toward inclusive education practices.

Table 6 represents the distribution of respondents based on the nature of the school in which they are employed.

Table 6: School Type

School Type		
Type of School	Frequency	Percentage
Government School	60	71.43
Private School	21	25.00
Aided School	3	3.57

■ Government — 71.43% ■ Private — 25.00%
■ Aided — 3.57%

Fig. 1 — School type distribution (N = 84)

■ Government ■ Private ■ Aided

Fig. 2 — Frequency by school type (N = 84)

Fig. 6: School Type

Out of the total 84 respondents, a majority, 60 teachers (71.43%) were working in government schools. On the contrary, 21 respondents (25.00%) were from private schools, while only 3 respondents (3.57%) were teaching in aided schools. This indicates that the sample was largely composed of teachers from government institutions, reflecting a strong representation from the public education sector.

Hypothesis Testing Results

The statistical analysis employed independent samples t-tests to examine five specific hypotheses at a 0.05 significance level. With 82 degrees of freedom and a critical t-value of ± 1.989 , all null hypotheses were accepted, indicating no statistically significant differences between TGT and PGT teachers across any measured dimension.

Table 7: t-test for Teacher Attitude Scale Toward Inclusive Education (TASTIE-SA)

Dimensions	Group	Mean	SD	t-value	Critical t-value	p-value	Result
Overall Attitudes	TGT	114.98	10.35	0.152	± 1.989	$p > 0.05$	NS
	PGT	114.64	9.93				

Psychological & Behavioral	TGT	26.17	3.85	0.384	±1.989	p > 0.05	NS
	PGT	3.52	3.52				
Social & Parental Involvement	TGT	30.98	3.87	-1.045	±1.989	p > 0.05	NS
	PGT	31.72	2.61				
Curricular & Co-curricular	TGT	31.63	4.97	0.074	±1.989	p > 0.05	NS
	PGT	31.56	3.71				
Administrative Aspects	TGT	26.21	2.52	1.222	±1.989	p > 0.05	NS
	PGT	25.50	2.71				

NS: Not Significant

Hypothesis 1 (Overall Attitudes): The calculated t-value of 0.152 fell well within the acceptance region, indicating no significant difference in overall attitudes toward inclusive education between TGT and PGT teachers.

Hypothesis 2 (Psychological and Behavioral Dimension): With a t-value of 0.384, the analysis showed no significant difference between teacher groups in their attitudes toward psychological and behavioral aspects of inclusive education.

Hypothesis 3 (Social and Parental Dimension): The t-value of -1.045 indicated no significant difference in attitudes toward social and parental involvement in inclusive education between the two teacher groups.

Hypothesis 4 (Curricular and Co-curricular Dimension): The extremely small t-value of 0.074 demonstrated virtually identical attitudes between TGT and PGT teachers regarding curricular and co-curricular aspects of inclusive education.

Hypothesis 5 (Administrative Dimension): With a t-value of 1.222, though representing the largest difference between groups, no significant variation was found in attitudes toward administrative aspects of inclusive education.

Table 7 represented independent sample t-tests, conducted to examine differences between TGT and PGT teachers in their overall attitudes and across the sub-dimensions of inclusive education. The analysis revealed that all null hypotheses were accepted, indicating no statistically significant differences between the two groups in overall attitudes, or in psychological-behavioral, social-parental, curricular-co-curricular, and administrative dimensions. This suggests that both TGT and PGT teachers share similar perspectives toward inclusive education, irrespective of their teaching category.

Discussions:

Overall Attitude Convergence

The most significant finding of this study is the remarkable convergence of attitudes between TGT and PGT teachers across all dimensions of inclusive education. The similarity in attitudes suggests that factors other than formal educational qualifications may play more crucial roles in shaping teachers' perspectives on inclusive education. These factors might include practical teaching experience, institutional culture, professional development opportunities, and exposure to students with diverse needs. The finding challenges the assumption that higher academic qualifications automatically translate to more positive or sophisticated attitudes toward inclusive education.

Psychological and Behavioral Dimension Analysis

The minimal difference between TGT and PGT teachers in the psychological and behavioral dimension ($t = 0.384$) reveals that both groups share similar perspectives on the emotional and psychological aspects of inclusive education. This finding suggests that teachers, regardless of their qualification level, recognize the importance of understanding student psychology and managing behavioral challenges in inclusive settings. This finding has important implications for teacher preparation programs, suggesting that both graduate and postgraduate programs may be providing similar foundations in understanding student psychology and behavior management.

Social and Parental Dimension Analysis

The negative t-value (-1.045) in the social and parental dimension, while not statistically significant, provides interesting insights into how different teacher groups perceive family and community involvement in inclusive education. The direction of the difference suggests that PGT teachers show a slightly higher mean score (-0.74 points higher), though this difference is not statistically significant, and the difference is not substantial enough to be statistically meaningful.

The convergence of attitudes in this dimension also suggests that both teacher groups may have similar experiences with parent and community interactions, regardless of their formal educational background. This finding supports the notion that practical experience in engaging with families and communities may be more influential than theoretical knowledge in shaping attitudes toward social and parental involvement.

Curricular and Co-curricular Dimension Analysis

The extremely small t-value (0.074) in the curricular and co-curricular dimension represents the closest convergence between TGT and PGT teachers. This finding suggests that both groups hold virtually identical attitudes toward curriculum adaptation and co-curricular activities in inclusive education settings.

The similarity in attitudes toward curricular and co-curricular aspects also suggests that both teacher groups may have similar levels of confidence and competence in making necessary adaptations. This finding indicates that curriculum adaptation skills may be developed more through practical experience than through formal educational preparation.

Administrative Dimension Analysis

The administrative dimension showed the largest difference between groups ($t = 1.222$), though still not statistically significant. This finding suggests that while both TGT and PGT teachers share similar overall perspectives on administrative support for inclusive education, there may be subtle differences in how they perceive institutional policies and administrative backing.

Dimensional Conclusions

Psychological and Behavioral Dimension: Both TGT and PGT teachers share similar perspectives on the emotional and psychological challenges of inclusive education, suggesting that practical experience may be more influential than theoretical knowledge in this area.

Social and Parental Dimension: Teachers across qualification levels recognize the importance of family and community involvement in inclusive education, indicating a shared understanding of the collaborative nature of inclusive practices.

Curricular and Co-curricular Dimension: The virtual identity in attitudes toward curriculum adaptation suggests that both teacher groups face similar challenges and have comparable competencies in modifying instructional approaches for diverse learners.

Administrative Dimension: While showing the largest difference, both teacher groups share similar concerns about administrative support for inclusive education, indicating systemic issues that transcend individual qualifications.

This finding suggests that administrative support for inclusive education may be perceived as inadequate by both teacher groups, regardless of their qualification level. The similarity in attitudes indicates that systemic issues with administrative support may be more influential than individual teachers.

Conclusion

The most significant conclusion of this study is that TGT and PGT teachers demonstrate statistically equivalent attitudes toward inclusive education across all measured dimensions. This finding fundamentally challenges the assumption that higher educational qualifications automatically translate to more positive or sophisticated attitudes toward inclusive practices.

This study has provided valuable insights into the attitudes of secondary school teachers toward inclusive education, revealing significant similarities between TGT and PGT teachers across all measured dimensions. The findings challenge common assumptions about the relationship between educational qualifications and professional attitudes, suggesting that other factors may be more influential in shaping teacher perspectives on inclusive education.

The implications of this research extend beyond the immediate context to inform policy development, teacher training programs, and institutional practices. By understanding that teachers across qualification levels share similar perspectives on inclusive education, stakeholders can develop more effective strategies for supporting inclusive practices and creating educational environments that serve all students effectively.

References

- Alur, M., & Bach, M. (2010). *The journey for inclusive education in the Indian subcontinent*. Routledge India.

- Avramidis, E., & Norwich, B. (2002). Teachers' attitudes towards integration/inclusion: A review of the literature. *European Journal of Special Needs Education, 17*(2), 129–147. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08856250210129056>
- Best, J. W., & Kahn, J. V. (2006). *Research in education* (10th ed.). Pearson Education.
- Bhattacharjee, R. (2021). A study of special education and inclusive education in India. *IMPACT: International Journal of Research in Humanities, Arts and Literature, 9*(5), 83–94.
- Bhatnagar, N., & Das, A. (2013). Nearly two decades after the implementation of persons with disabilities act: Concerns of Indian teachers to implement inclusive education. *International Journal of Special Education, 28*(1), 104–113.
- Cohen, L., Manion, L., & Morrison, K. (2018). *Research methods in education* (8th ed.). Routledge.
- Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research* (4th ed.). Pearson Education.
- Florian, L., & Black-Hawkins, K. (2011). Exploring inclusive pedagogy. *British Educational Research Journal, 37*(5), 813–828. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01411926.2010.501096>
- Forlin, C., & Chambers, D. (2011). Teacher preparation for inclusive education: Increasing knowledge but raising concerns. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Teacher Education, 39*(1), 17–32.
- Gay, L. R., Mills, G. E., & Airasian, P. (2011). *Educational research: Competencies for analysis and applications* (10th ed.). Pearson Education.
- Gay, L. R., Mills, G. E., & Airasian, P. W. (2012). *Educational research: Competencies for analysis and applications* (10th ed.). Pearson Education.
- Hossain, A. (2021). Inclusive education in India: Opportunities and challenges. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts, 9*(1), 4487–4491.
- Köb, S., & Janz, F. (2021). Teachers' subjective theories regarding social dynamics, management, and social participation of students with intellectual disabilities in inclusive classrooms. *International Journal of Inclusive Education, 27*(14), 1503–1543. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2021.1902002>

- Kurowski, M., Černý, M., & Trapl, F. (2022). A review study of research articles on the barriers to inclusive education in primary schools. *Journal on Efficiency and Responsibility in Education and Science*, 15(2), 116–130. <https://doi.org/10.7160/eriesj.2022.150206>
- Lalvani, P. (2015). Rethinking disability and inclusive education: A teacher study group. *Review of Disability Studies: An International Journal*, 11(3), 1–15.
- Leijen, Ä., Arcidiacono, F., & Baucal, A. (2021). The dilemma of inclusive education: Inclusion for some or inclusion for all. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 633066. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.633066>
- Makwana, G. (2022). The concept of inclusive education in India. *International Journal of Educational Research and Development*, 4(2), 112–135.
- Madhesh, A. (2023). The concept of inclusive education from the point of view of academics specialising in special education at Saudi universities. *Humanities & Social Sciences Communications*, 10, 278. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-023-01802-y>
- Mann, G., & Gilmore, L. (2021). Barriers to positive parent–teacher partnerships: The views of parents and teachers in an inclusive education context. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 27(14), 1503–1515. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2021.1900426>
- Mehta, S. (2020). Inclusive education: Implementation with effectiveness. *BSSS Journal of Education*, 9(1), 45–52.
- Ministry of Human Resource Development. (2009). *The Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act, 2009*. Government of India.
- Ministry of Human Resource Development. (2020). *National Education Policy 2020*. Government of India.
- Ministry of Law and Justice. (2016). *The Rights of Persons with Disabilities Act, 2016*. Government of India.
- Mishra, M. K., & Negari, W. (2021). Analytical study of inclusive education in India. *IJARIE*, 7(3), 2612–2616.

- Moberg, S., & Savolainen, H. (2003). Struggling for inclusive education in the North and the South: Educators' perceptions in Finland and Zambia. *International Journal of Rehabilitation Research*, 26(1), 21–31. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00004356-200303000-00005>
- Nilholm, C. (2021). Research about inclusive education in 2020: How can we improve our theories to change practice? *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, 36(3), 434–447. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08856257.2020.1754547>
- Parey, B. (2021). Exploring positive and negative teachers' attitudes towards inclusion of children with disabilities in schools in Trinidad. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 27(14), 1544–1558. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2021.1902004>
- Pingle, S., & Garg, I. (2015). Effect of inclusive education awareness programme on preservice teachers. *The European Conference on Education Proceedings*, 1–20.
- Safdar, S., & Rashid, S. (2021). Preparation of pre-service teachers for inclusive classrooms: Challenges and prospects. *Elementary Education Online*, 20(4), 2785–2792.
- Sharma, U., & Das, A. (2015). Inclusive education in India: Past, present, and future. *Support for Learning*, 30(1), 55–68.
- Singh, J. D. (2016). Inclusive education in India: Concept, need and challenges. *Scholarly Research Journal for Humanity Science and English Language*, 3(17), 3222–3232.
- Singh, S. K. (2017). A study of inclusive education with reference to visually impaired students. *International Journal of Science Technology and Management*, 6(6), 179–185.
- Sood, V., & Anand, A. (2010). *Teacher attitude scale toward inclusive education (TASTIE-SA)*. National Psychological Corporation.
- UNESCO. (1994). *The Salamanca statement and framework for action on special needs education*.
- UNESCO. (2009). *Policy guidelines on inclusion in education*.
- UNESCO. (2020). *Inclusion and education: All means all (Global education monitoring report)*.
- Yadav, S. (2023). Inclusive education in India: Issues, challenges and prospects. *International Journal of Advanced Education and Research*, 8(1), 14–16.